

Vocational Guidance and its Strategies

Dr.C.Thenmozhi

*Principal, Adhiparasakthi College of Education
G.B.Nagar, Kalavai, Vellore, Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

A person's performance for a vocation is influenced by the aspirations and choice of their parents. This may result in an unsatisfactory placement of the student. However, it is important to note that the vocational choice should be decided more on the individual's ability, interest, aptitude, rather than on parental aspirations alone. Some individuals are often found to be dissatisfied in the work they are doing and are not properly adjusted, to the work environment leading to frustration, state of stress, diminished productivity, etc. An Unfavourable attitude of any individual is not conducive for the work culture in any organization. Efforts must consciously be made by educational institutions to work towards developing a positive attitude towards work in their students. If this can be done in the institution, it can be expected that there would be a transfer of this in the work situation. The success or failure of a person in a vocation depends upon, many others factors including satisfaction one derives from the vocation. satisfaction results from working in harmony with one's own potentialities, strengths, weaknesses, etc. A well organized system of vocational information readily available to students and set up which encourages students and trains them to find out the available information about careers, from the basis for the choice of vocational e strategies.

Introduction

Man's attitude to something which takes up much, if not most, of his working hours, has rarely been neutral. Work has been seen as a necessary evil, as one of the virtues that pave the path to heaven, as the most important way in which an individual contributes to his society, and as a major instrument of self-realisation. In the process of vocational guidance, the individual is assisted to understand his abilities, and limitations and accept them. Once he is aware of his potentialities, he is helped to make use of the available opportunities. For the effectiveness of vocational guidance, the student's goals, needs, and interests are also taken into account. Students may face many difficulties in the choice of a vocation, vocational persuasion and vocational adjustment. This often leads to several ills such as students not getting proper jobs, encountering difficulties in getting on well with the job, etc. This implies that students should discover their capabilities. They must relate the information they acquire about their career to their own capabilities.

Definitions of Guidance

Morris,Ruth strang," Guidance is a process of helping every individual, through his own efforts, to discover and developing his potentialities for his personal happiness and social usefulness."

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Arthur.J.Jones, "Guidance is the personal help that is given by one person to another in developing life goals, in making adjustment, and in solving problems, that confront him in the attainment of goals".

Vocational Guidance

Although vocational guidance is a recent concept, it has undergone a radical change. The old concept of vocational guidance was fitting an individual to a job -square peg in a square hole. But this is too limited a view. It is wrong to assume that men are really born to fit in various professions. a person is born for no profession at birth. He does possess some specific ability, but that will help him to take up no one specific job but a variety of jobs, jobs of a particular group. He can further take up some jobs, nicely after the necessary orientation. It is wrong to presume that once a person has joined a profession, guidance has finished its task. Success in a job depends upon not only entry but also systematic progress and adjustment during employment. Hence there is need for re-orientation of the very purpose of vocational guidance.

Definitions of Vocational Guidance

Frank Pearson wrote nearly unity years ago about the definition of vocational guidance. "The vocation bureau is intended to aid young people in choosing an occupation, preparing themselves for it finding an opening in for it and building up a career of efficiency and success".

According to The National Vocational Guidance Association of America 1937,"The vocational guidance is the process of assisting the individuals to choose an occupation, prepare for it, enter upon and progress in it. It is concerned primarily with helping individuals make decision and choices involved in planning a future, and building a career decision, and choics necessary in affecting satisfactory vocational adjustment".

Need of Vocational Guidance

According to Myer's, Vocational guidance is needed because of the following reasons:

- a. Vocational guidance provides many economic advantages to the employers. Their problems

are less because then workers enjoy job satisfaction.

- b. Human potentialities are utilized to a maximum with the help of vocational guidance. We are then truly benefitted by it.
- c. If an individual stays in a wrong profession, he suffers from pshchic loss. The individual is not happy. He is frustrated. His family life is affected.
- d. If an individual stays in a wrong profession for a time, he suffers economically – there is a financial loss.
- e. There are a large number of personal and social values of vocational guidance. Leaving aside financial considerations, the worker's happiness, his personal development, his value as a social unit and his contribution to human welfare are all involved. Right vocational guidance helps us to achieve that.
- f. It is needed from the point of view of health of the workers. If the profession is such where health of social workers breaks down, production suffers and morale of workers goes down.

Purpose of Vocational Guidance

The purpose of vocational guidance is:

- a. To serve the individual and the society
- b. To prevent maladjustment and dissatisfaction
- c. To ensure efficient use of man power

Primary Aim of Vocational Guidance

The primary aim of vocational guidance is the promotion of personal satisfaction with life as a whole. As such, the process of vocational guidance will consists of the following factors:

- a. providing a placement service to help him/her to implement those plans
- b. providing a follow-up service to help him /her to implement those plans.
- c. enabling the individual to discover information about himself/herself, his/her abilities, interests, needs, ambitions, limitations and their causes.
- d. providing counseling in order to promote self understanding and to develop educational and occupational plans.

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| <p>e. providing him/her with a frame of reference in which to see himself / herself, in relation to these educational and vocational opportunities; to orient him/ her to the helping agencies available and to alert him /her to future decision making points in his/ her career.</p> <p>f. providing him/her with information</p> <p>g. n about his/her environment, the advantages and disadvantages of different occupations and educational courses, the qualifications, necessary for entry into them, and the total range of opportunities available to him/her in theory and practice.</p> | <p>a. Create the habit of neat and systematic work.</p> <p>b. Create love and respect – positive attitude for normal work.</p> <p>c. Encourage neatness in work.</p> <p>d. Train the use of the hands of the child.</p> <p>e. Encourage the development of good relations amongst themselves.</p> <p>f. Create and achieve hand-eye co-ordination.</p> |
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The purpose of vocational guidance is to help the child through the curriculum and the extra curriculum to develop his /her basic skills and attitudes which are important for successful work. There are essential requirements for a good worker, whatever be the field, for example , doing the job earnestly in a neat and systematic manner, using what one possesses to an optimum extent, doing it in co-operation with others. habits of doing work and proper attitudes towards work may be developed.

Role of Education in Vocational Guidance and Vocational Education

The two terms are closely related but are not synonymous. Vocational education where vocational guidance, in a way, ends. Vocational guidance without vocational education is a waste. Vocational education is a necessary preparation or training undergone before an individual enters a vocation chosen through vocational guidance. The student's choice of courses and his/her vocational plans are functionally interrelated. Educational guidance becomes fruitful only by keeping an eye on the vocational implications of subjects and the field of occupations they will lead to. Similarly, a plan of vocational guidance must be followed or accompanied by educational guidance. In vocational guidance, the vocational considerations, dominate, whereas in educational guidance, "making a life in school" is more important than "making a living" after the school years. Vocational education begins when vocational guidance ends. The programme of vocational guidance is of vital importance at the secondary and the college stages. Herein the person is to be finally told as to which vocation is fit for him. He is to be helped in the choice and is to be prepared to enter in to it.

Stages in Vocational Guidance

Vocational guidance at the Elementary Stage

Not much can be done at the elementary stage strictly in terms of guidance worker can do the following:

Vocational guidance at the Secondary Stage Objectives

- a. helping pupils according to their vocational assets and liabilities
- b. helping pupils to get suitable jobs
- c. helping pupils to prepare themselves for entry into the careers of their choice
- d. helping pupils to be familiar with occupations and their requirements
- e. helping pupils to be familiar with vocational implications of different subjects to be studied in the secondary school.

Definite guidance in vocations can be given at this stage, for example:

- a. The child should be helped to make the right choice now here.
- b. The child should be helped to know himself. Entire vocational guidance depends on it.
- c. familiarity about the world or work can be given.
- d. The child can be placed during a high school in a suitable job and follow-up may be undertaken.
- e. Whether the child will go to college or remain in a job can also be decided.

Vocational Guidance Strategies

Vocational guidance strategies are based on the following principles:

- Vocational guidance services should be based on the principle of individual differences.
- Different strategies need to be used to cater to the individual vocational needs of students.
- The individual needs to understand the total perspective of a vocation for which he has decided to prepare himself.
- Vocational guidance service must fulfill the vocational needs of every student.
- The selection of a particular vocation is not confined to a single, fixed decision, but a time extending process, involving a series of social and personal factors.
- Occupation is to be looked at as a source of income to people and a major source of satisfying needs and optimizing aptitudes, competencies and interests.

Conclusion

The vocational guidance is a long continuous process which begins in the school and is needed throughout the working life of the individual. It is aimed at wise use by the person of priceless native capacity and the results of costly training provided by the school for the good of the individual and the society. Vocational guidance is complex. In the end it may be added that in most of the Indian schools, the facilities for educational and vocational guidance are 'non-existent'. Vocational guidance can be given to individual as well as to a group. When an individual faces any vocational problem like selection of a vocation, adjustment in vocation, etc., individual guidance is given to him. On the other hand, if a similar vocational problem is faced by a group, a group guidance programme can be organized.

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